

GROUP DIFFERENCE CORDIAL LABELING IN THE PATH UNION OF JOIN ZERO DIVISOR GRAPHS

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Received: Jun 25, 2025

Accepted: July 20, 2025

Published: July 24, 2025

ABSTRACT:

Let G be a (p, q) graph and let A be a group. Let $f: V(G) \rightarrow A$ be a map. For each edge uv assign the label $|o(f(u)) - o(f(v))|$. For $u, v \in V$ here $o(f(u))$ denotes the order of $f(u)$ as an element of the group A . f is called a group difference cordial labeling if the following conditions hold:

- (1) For $x, y \in A$, $|v_f(x) - v_f(y)| \leq 1$, where $v_f(x)$ is the number of vertices labeled with x .
- (2) For $i, j \in I$, $|e_f(i) - e_f(j)| \leq 1$, where $e_f(i)$ is the number of edges labeled with i .

A graph with a group difference cordial labeling is called a group difference cordial graph. In this paper, we take A as the group of elements 1 and -1 and we prove that path union of Join Zero-Divisor graphs are group difference cordial graphs.

KEY WORDS: Zero-divisor graphs, Path union, cordial graphs, Difference cordial labeling, Group difference cordial labeling, Group difference cordial graphs.

1.INTRODUCTION:

Let $G = (V(G), E(G))$ be a simple, finite and undirected graph. A graph labelling is the assignment of the integers to vertices, edges or both if certain conditions have been met.

If the domain of the mapping is the set of vertices (or edges), then the labeling is vertex labeling (or an edge labeling). Cahit [2] developed the idea of cordial labeling from both graceful and harmonious labeling.

In practical situations labeling is mainly applied radar pulse code design, neural networks, addressing systems in communication networks and in frequency assignment problem Hale using graph labeling some interesting games and puzzles have been solved. Signed product cordial labeling is a modified version of cordial labeling which was introduced by [12] Babujee and Loganathan and they proved for path graphs, Trees and cycles admits signed product cordial. The concept of the Coloring Zero divisor graphs of commutative ring was introduced by I. Beck [3]. Let R be a commutative ring with non-zero identity, $Z(R)$ it's set of all zero devisors in R and $Z^*(R) = Z(R) \setminus \{0\}$. The Zero-divisor graph of R is the simple undirected graph $\Gamma(R)$ with vertex set $Z^*(R)$ and two distinct vertices x and y are adjacent if $xy = 0$. All graphs consider in this paper are finite, simple and undirected. [10] S. Sajana and D. Bharathi studied the Intersection graph of zero-divisors of a finite commutative ring. [11]

D. Eswara Rao and D. Bharathi studied the Total zero divisor graph of a commutative Ring.

M. Lakshmi, D. Bharathi [13][14] proved SDC labeling on path union and cycle of zero divisor graphs and join zero divisor graphs. In this study we investigated the existence of group difference cordial labeling of zero-divisor graphs.

2.PRELIMINARIES:

Definition: 2.1

For a commutative ring Z_n with unity ($1 \neq 0$), the zero-divisor graph of Z_n , denoted by $\Gamma(Z_n)$, is a simple graph with vertices as elements of Z_n and two distinct vertices are adjacent whenever the product of the vertices is zero.

Definition 2.2

Let R be a finite ring. An element $a \in R$ is called a zero divisor if there exists a non-zero element $b \in R$ such that

$$a \cdot b = 0 \text{ or } b \cdot a = 0.$$

Definition 2.3

The path union of a graph G is the graph obtained by adding an edge between corresponding vertices of G_1 to G_{i+1} , $1 \leq i \leq n-1$, Where $G_1, G_2, G_3, \dots, G_n$ ($n \geq 2$) are n copies of G . It is denoted by $P(n, G)$.

Definition 2.4

A graph G is said to be complete if every pair of its distinct vertices are adjacent.

Definition 2.5

A bipartite graph is a graph whose vertex set $V(G)$ can be partitioned into two subsets V_1 and V_2 such that every edge of G has one end in V_1 and the other end in V_2 . (V_1, V_2) is called a bipartition of G .

Definition 2.6

A complete bipartite graph is a bipartite graph with bipartition (V_1, V_2) such that every vertex of V_1 is joined to all the vertices of V_2 . It is denoted by $K_{m,n}$ where $|V_1| = m$ and $|V_2| = n$.

A star graph is a complete bipartite graph $K_{1,n}$.

Definition 2.7

A cordial labeling is a binary vertex and edge labeling of a graph that satisfies certain conditions $|v_f(0) - v_f(1)| \leq 1$ and $|e_f(0) - e_f(1)| \leq 1$. $v_f(0)$ and $v_f(1)$ are the number of vertices in G with label 0 and label 1 under f respectively.

$e_f(0)$ and $e_f(1)$ are the number of edges in G with label 0 and label 1 under f respectively.

Definition 2.8

A mapping $f: V(G) \rightarrow \{0,1\}$ is called binary vertex labeling of G and $f(v)$ is called label of vertex v of G under f .

Let $|v_f(0)|$ and $|v_f(1)|$ be the number of vertices of G labeled with 0 and 1 respectively under f .

A mapping $f^*: E(G) \rightarrow \{0,1\}$ is called binary edge labeling of G . Let $|e_{f^*}(0)|, |e_{f^*}(1)|$ the number of edges of G having labels 0 and 1 respectively under f^* .

Definition 2.9

A graph G with p vertices and q edges and let A be a group. Let $f: V(G) \rightarrow A$ be a map. For each edge uv assign the label $|o(f(u)) - o(f(v))|$, here $o(f(u))$ denotes the order of $f(u)$ as an element of the group A . Let I be the set of all integers that are labels of the edges of G . f is called a group difference cordial labeling. If the following conditions hold:

- (1) For $x, y \in A, |v_f(x) - v_f(y)| \leq 1$, where $v_f(x)$ is the number of vertices labeled with x .
- (2) For $i, j \in I, |e_f(i) - e_f(j)| \leq 1$, where $e_f(i)$ denotes the number of edges labeled with i .

A graph with a group difference cordial labeling is called a group difference cordial graph. In this paper, we take A as the group of elements 1 and -1 or $\{1, -1\}$ and prove that corona product of cycle and Zero-Divisor graph are group difference cordial graphs.

3. MAIN RESULT

Here we discuss path union of join zero-divisor graphs which admit a GDC labeling.

Theorem 3.1. For any prime number $p > 2$ and $n \geq 2$ the path union graph $P(n, (\Gamma(Z_{2p}) + \Gamma(Z_4)))$ is Group difference cordial graph.

Proof:

The vertex set and edge set of $(\Gamma(Z_{2p}) + \Gamma(Z_4))$ are

$$V(\Gamma(Z_{2p}) + \Gamma(Z_4)) = \{u_1, u_2, u_3, \dots, u_{p-1}, u_p, x\}, \text{ where } x=2 \in Z_4$$

$$E(\Gamma(Z_{2p}) + \Gamma(Z_4)) = \{u_i u_p, u_i x, u_p x \mid 1 \leq i \leq p-1\}.$$

$$|V(\Gamma(Z_{2p}) + \Gamma(Z_4))| = p+1 \text{ and } |E(\Gamma(Z_{2p}) + \Gamma(Z_4))| = 2p-1.$$

$$\text{Let } G = P(n, (\Gamma(Z_{2p}) + \Gamma(Z_4)))$$

Let the vertex set of G

$$V(G) = \{u_{1,1}, u_{1,2}, \dots, u_{1,p-1}, u_{1,p}, x_1, u_{2,1}, u_{2,2}, \dots, u_{2,p-1}, u_{2,p}, x_2, \dots, u_{n,1}, u_{n,2}, \dots, u_{n,p-1}, u_{n,p}, x_n\}$$

Also, the edge set of G

$$E(G) = \{u_{1,i} u_{1,p}, u_{1,i} x_1, u_{1,p} x_1, u_{2,i} u_{2,p}, u_{2,i} x_2, \dots, u_{n,i} u_{n,p}, u_{n,i} x_n, u_{1,p} u_{2,p}, u_{2,p} u_{3,p}, \dots, u_{n-1,p} u_{n,p} \mid 1 \leq i \leq p-1\}.$$

Note that,

$$|V(G)| = n(p+1) \text{ and } |E(G)| = n(2p-1) + (n-1).$$

Define the vertex labeling $f: V(G) \rightarrow \{-1,1\}$ by

$$f(u_{1,p}) = (-1), f(u_{1,k}) = (-1)^{k+1} \text{ for } 1 \leq k \leq p-1 \text{ and } f(x_1) = 1$$

$$f(u_{2,p}) = (-1), f(u_{2,k}) = (-1)^{k+1} \text{ for } 1 \leq k \leq p-1 \text{ and } f(x_2) = 1$$

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$$f(u_{n,p}) = (-1), f(u_{n,k}) = (-1)^{k+1} \text{ for } 1 \leq k \leq p-1 \text{ and } f(x_n) = 1.$$

Clearly

$$|v_f(-1)| = \frac{n(p+1)}{2} \text{ and } |v_f(1)| = \frac{n(p+1)}{2}$$

the induced edge labeling $f^*: E(G) \rightarrow \{0,1\}$ is given by

$$f^*(u_{1,i}u_{1,p}) = \begin{cases} 1 & i \text{ is odd;} \\ 0 & i \text{ is even.} \end{cases} \quad 1 \leq i \leq p-1$$

$$f^*(u_{2,i}u_{2,p}) = \begin{cases} 1 & i \text{ is odd;} \\ 0 & i \text{ is even.} \end{cases} \quad 1 \leq i \leq p-1$$

$$f^*(u_{1,i}x_1) = \begin{cases} 1 & i \text{ is even;} \\ 0 & i \text{ is odd.} \end{cases} \quad 1 \leq i \leq p-1$$

$$f^*(u_{2,i}x_2) = \begin{cases} 1 & i \text{ is even;} \\ 0 & i \text{ is odd.} \end{cases} \quad 1 \leq i \leq p-1$$

⋮

$$f^*(u_{1,p}x_1) = 1, f^*(u_{n,i}x_n) = \begin{cases} 1 & i \text{ is even;} \\ 0 & i \text{ is odd.} \end{cases} \quad 1 \leq i \leq p-1$$

$$f^*(u_{2,p}x_2) = 1, f^*(u_{n,i}u_{n,p}) = \begin{cases} 1 & i \text{ is odd;} \\ 0 & i \text{ is even.} \end{cases} \quad 1 \leq i \leq p-1$$

⋮

$$f^*(u_{n,p}x_n) = 1, f^*(u_{i,p}u_{i+1,p}) = 0; \quad 1 \leq i \leq n-1$$

From the above $|e_{f^*}(1)| = np$ and $|e_{f^*}(0)| = n(p-1) + (n-1) = np - 1$

Thus $|e_{f^*}(0) - e_{f^*}(1)| \leq 1$.

Therefore, G is a group difference cordial graph.

Example 3.2:

$P(3, (\Gamma(Z_{10}) + \Gamma(Z_4)))$ admits the group difference cordial labeling is given in figure 5.

Here we take $n=3, p=5$

$$V(\Gamma(Z_{10}) + \Gamma(Z_4)) = \{u_1, u_2, u_3, \dots, u_{p-1}, u_p, x\}, \text{ where } x=2 \in Z_4$$

$$V(\Gamma(Z_{10}) + \Gamma(Z_4)) = \{2,4,6,8,5,2\}.$$

let $G = P(3, (\Gamma(Z_{10}) + \Gamma(Z_4)))$

The vertex set of G is

$$V(G) = \{u_{1,1}, u_{1,2}, u_{1,3}, u_{1,4}, u_{1,5}, x_1, u_{2,1}, u_{2,2}, u_{2,3}, u_{2,4}, u_{2,5}, x_2, u_{3,1}, u_{3,2}, u_{3,3}, u_{3,4}, u_{3,5}, x_3\}$$

Also, the edge set of G is

$$E(G) = \{u_{1,i}u_{1,5}, u_{1,i}x_1, u_{1,5}x_1, u_{2,i}u_{2,5}, u_{2,5}x_2, u_{2,i}x_2, u_{3,i}u_{3,5}, u_{3,i}x_3, u_{3,5}x_3, u_{1,5}u_{2,5}, u_{2,5}u_{3,5}; 1 \leq i \leq 4\}.$$

Note that

$$|V(G)| = 18 \text{ and } |E(G)| = 29.$$

Define the vertex labeling $f: V(G) \rightarrow \{-1,1\}$ by

$$f(u_{1,5}) = (-1), f(u_{1,k}) = (-1)^{k+1} \text{ for } 1 \leq k \leq 4 \text{ and } f(x_1) = 1$$

$$f(u_{2,5}) = (-1), f(u_{2,k}) = (-1)^{k+1} \text{ for } 1 \leq k \leq 4 \text{ and } f(x_2) = 1$$

$$f(u_{3,5}) = (-1), f(u_{3,k}) = (-1)^{k+1} \text{ for } 1 \leq k \leq 4 \text{ and } f(x_3) = 1.$$

Clearly

$$|v_f(-1)| = 9 \text{ and } |v_f(1)| = 9$$

The induced edge labeling

$$f^*: E(G) \rightarrow \{0,1\} \text{ is given by}$$

$$f^*(u_{1,i}u_{1,5}) = \begin{cases} 1 & i \text{ is odd;} \\ 0 & i \text{ is even.} \end{cases} \quad 1 \leq i \leq 4$$

$$f^*(u_{2,i}u_{2,5}) = \begin{cases} 1 & i \text{ is odd;} \\ 0 & i \text{ is even.} \end{cases} \quad 1 \leq i \leq 4$$

$$f^*(u_{3,i}u_{3,5}) = \begin{cases} 1 & i \text{ is odd;} \\ 0 & i \text{ is even.} \end{cases} \quad 1 \leq i \leq 4$$

$$f^*(u_{1,i}x_1) = \begin{cases} 1 & i \text{ is even} \\ 0 & i \text{ is odd} \end{cases}; 1 \leq i \leq 4$$

$$f^*(u_{2,i}x_2) = \begin{cases} 1 & i \text{ is even} \\ 0 & i \text{ is odd} \end{cases}; 1 \leq i \leq 4$$

$$f^*(u_{3,i}x_3) = \begin{cases} 1 & i \text{ is even} \\ 0 & i \text{ is odd} \end{cases}; 1 \leq i \leq 4$$

From the above $|e_{f^*}(1)| = 15$ and $|e_{f^*}(0)| = 14$

Thus, $|e_{f^*}(0) - e_{f^*}(1)| \leq 1$.

Therefore, G is a group difference cordial graph.

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figure 5. P (3. (Γ(Z₁₀) + Γ(Z₄)))

Theorem 3.3. For any prime number $p > 2$ and $n= 2$ the path union graph $P(n, (\Gamma(Z_{2p}) + \Gamma(Z_9)))$ admits Group difference cordial labeling.

Proof:

The vertex and edge set of $(\Gamma(Z_{2p}) + \Gamma(Z_9))$ are

$$V(\Gamma(Z_{2p}) + \Gamma(Z_9)) = \{u_1, u_2, u_3, \dots, u_{p-1}, u_p, x, y\}$$

$$= \{2, 4, \dots, 2(p-1), p, x, y\} \text{ where } x=3 \text{ and } y=6 \in Z_9$$

$$E(\Gamma(Z_{2p}) + \Gamma(Z_9)) = \{u_i u_p, u_i x, u_i y, u_p x, u_p y, x y / 1 \leq i \leq p - 1\}.$$

$$|V(\Gamma(Z_{2p}) + \Gamma(Z_9))| = p+2 \text{ and } |E(\Gamma(Z_{2p}) + \Gamma(Z_9))| = 3p.$$

Let $G = P(2, (\Gamma(Z_{2p}) + \Gamma(Z_9)))$

The vertex set of G is

$$V(G) = \{u_{1,1}, u_{1,2}, \dots, u_{1,p-1}, u_{1,p}, x_1, y_1, u_{2,1}, u_{2,2}, \dots, u_{2,p-1}, u_{2,p}, x_2, y_2\}$$

Also, the edge set of G is

$$E(G) = \{u_{1,i} u_{1,p}, u_{1,i} x_1, u_{1,i} y_1, u_{1,p} x_1, u_{1,p} y_1, x_1 y_1, u_{2,i} u_{2,p}, u_{2,p} x_2, u_{2,i} x_2, u_{2,i} y_2, u_{2,p} x_2 y_2, u_{1,p} u_{2,p}; 1 \leq i \leq p - 1\}.$$

Note that

$$|V(G)| = 2(p+2) \text{ and } |E(G)| = 6p+1.$$

Define the vertex labeling $f: V(G) \rightarrow \{-1, 1\}$ by

$$f(u_{1,p}) = (-1), f(u_{1,k}) = (-1)^{k+1} \text{ for } 1 \leq k \leq p - 1 \text{ and } f(x_1) = 1, f(y_1) = -1$$

$$f(u_{2,p}) = 1, f(u_{2,k}) = (-1)^k \text{ for } 1 \leq k \leq p - 1 \text{ and } f(x_2) = -1, f(y_2) = 1$$

Clearly,

$$|v_f(-1)| = p+2 \text{ and } |v_f(1)| = p + 2.$$

the induced edge labeling $f^*: E(G) \rightarrow \{0,1\}$ is given by

$$f^*(u_{1,i} u_{1,p}) = \begin{cases} 1 & i \text{ is odd} \\ 0 & i \text{ is even} \end{cases}; 1 \leq i \leq p - 1$$

$$f^*(u_{2,i}u_{2,p}) = \begin{cases} 1 & i \text{ is odd}; 1 \leq i \leq p-1 \\ 0 & i \text{ is even}. \end{cases}$$

$$f^*(u_{1,i}x_1) = \begin{cases} 1 & i \text{ is even}; 1 \leq i \leq p-1 \\ 0 & i \text{ is odd}. \end{cases}$$

$$f^*(u_{1,i}y_1) = \begin{cases} 0 & i \text{ is even}; 1 \leq i \leq p-1 \\ 1 & i \text{ is odd}. \end{cases}$$

$$f^*(u_{2,i}x_2) = \begin{cases} 1 & i \text{ is even}; 1 \leq i \leq p-1 \\ 0 & i \text{ is odd}. \end{cases}$$

$$f^*(u_{2,i}y_2) = \begin{cases} 0 & i \text{ is even}; 1 \leq i \leq p-1 \\ 1 & i \text{ is odd}. \end{cases}$$

$$f^*(x_1y_1) = 1,$$

$$f^*(x_2y_2) = 1,$$

$$f^*(u_{1,p}u_{2,p}) = 1.$$

From the above $|e_{f^*}(1)| = 3(p-1) + 4$ and $|e_{f^*}(0)| = 3(p-1) + 3$

Then, $|e_{f^*}(0) - e_{f^*}(1)| \leq 1$.

Therefore, G is a group difference cordial graph.

Example 3.4: $P(2, (\Gamma(Z_{10}) + \Gamma(Z_9)))$ admits the group difference cordial labeling is given in figure 6.

The vertex and edge set of $(\Gamma(Z_{2p}) + \Gamma(Z_9))$ are

$$V(\Gamma(Z_{10}) + \Gamma(Z_9)) = \{2, 4, 6, 8, 5, 3, 6\} = \{u_1, u_2, u_3, u_4, u_5, x, y\}$$

$$E(\Gamma(Z_{10}) + \Gamma(Z_9)) = \{u_i u_5, u_i x, u_i y, u_5 x, u_5 y, x y / 1 \leq i \leq 4\}.$$

$$|V(\Gamma(Z_{10}) + \Gamma(Z_9))| = 7 \text{ and } |E(\Gamma(Z_{2p}) + \Gamma(Z_9))| = 15.$$

Let $G = P(2, (\Gamma(Z_{10}) + \Gamma(Z_9)))$ where $p=5$ and $n=2$

$$|V(G)| = 14 \text{ and } |E(G)| = 31.$$

Define the vertex labeling $f: V(G) \rightarrow \{-1, 1\}$

$$|v_f(-1)| = 7 \text{ and } |v_f(1)| = 7.$$

the induced edge labeling $f^*: E(G) \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$

$$\text{here } |e_{f^*}(1)| = 16 \text{ and } |e_{f^*}(0)| = 15$$

$$\text{then } |e_{f^*}(0) - e_{f^*}(1)| \leq 1.$$

Therefore, G is a group difference cordial graph.

figure 6. $P(2, (\Gamma(Z_{10}) + \Gamma(Z_9)))$

Corollary 3.5. For any prime number $p > 2$, the path union graph $P(n, (\Gamma(Z_{2p}) + \overline{\Gamma(Z_9)}))$, $n=2$ does not admit Group difference cordial labeling.

Example 3.6:

Let $G = P(2, (\Gamma(Z_{10}) + \overline{\Gamma(Z_9)}))$ where $p=5$

$$|V(G)| = 14 \text{ and } |E(G)| = 29.$$

Define the vertex labeling $f: V(G) \rightarrow \{-1, 1\}$

$$|v_f(-1)| = 7 \text{ and } |v_f(1)| = 7.$$

the induced edge labeling $f^*: E(G) \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$

here $|e_{f^*}(1)| = 14$ and $|e_{f^*}(0)| = 16$

$$\text{then } |e_{f^*}(0) - e_{f^*}(1)| \not\leq 1.$$

Therefore, G is not a group difference cordial graph in figure 7.

figure 7. $P(2, (\Gamma(Z_{10}) + \overline{\Gamma(Z_9)}))$

Theorem 3.7. For any prime number $p > 2$ and $n \geq 2$, the path union graph $P(n, (\Gamma(Z_{2p}) + \Gamma(Z_6)))$, is a Group difference cordial graph.

Proof:

The vertex and edge set of $(\Gamma(Z_{2p}) + \Gamma(Z_6))$ are

$$V(\Gamma(Z_{2p}) + \Gamma(Z_6)) = \{u_1, u_2, u_3, \dots, u_{p-1}, u_p, x, y, z\}$$

$$= \{2, 4, \dots, 2(p-1), p, x, y, z\} \text{ where } x=2 \text{ and } y=3 \text{ and } z = 4 \in Z_6$$

$$E(\Gamma(Z_{2p}) + \Gamma(Z_6)) = \{u_i u_p, u_i x, u_i y, u_i z, u_p x, u_p y, u_p z, x y, y z / 1 \leq i \leq p-1\}.$$

$$|V(\Gamma(Z_{2p}) + \Gamma(Z_6))| = p+3 \text{ and } |E(\Gamma(Z_{2p}) + \Gamma(Z_6))| = 4p+1.$$

Let $G = P(n, (\Gamma(Z_{2p}) + \Gamma(Z_6)))$, The vertex set of the graph G is

$$V(G) = \{u_{1,1}, u_{1,2}, \dots, u_{1,p-1}, u_{1,p}, x_1, y_1, z_1,$$

$$u_{2,1}, u_{2,2}, \dots, u_{2,p-1}, u_{2,p}, x_2, y_2, z_2,$$

$$\dots$$

$$\dots$$

$$\dots$$

$$u_{n,1}, u_{n,2}, \dots, u_{n,p-1}, u_{n,p}, x_n, y_n, z_n\}$$

and the edge set of G is

$$E(G) = \{u_{1,i} u_{1,p}, u_{1,p} x_1, u_{1,i} y_1, u_{1,i} z_1, u_{1,p} x_1, u_{1,p} y_1, u_{1,p} z_1, x_1 y_1, y_1 z_1,$$

$$u_{2,i} u_{2,p}, u_{2,i} x_2, u_{2,i} y_2, u_{2,i} z_2, u_{2,p} x_2, u_{2,p} y_2, u_{2,p} z_2, x_2 y_2, y_2 z_2,$$

$$\dots$$

$$\dots$$

$$\dots$$

$$u_{n,i} u_{n,p}, u_{n,i} x_n, u_{n,i} y_n, u_{n,i} z_n, u_{n,p} x_n, u_{n,p} y_n, u_{n,p} z_n, x_n y_n, y_n z_n,$$

$$u_{1,p} u_{2,p}, u_{2,p} u_{3,p}, \dots, u_{n-1,p} u_{n,p}, 1 \leq i \leq p-1\}$$

Note that

$$|V(G)| = np + 3n \text{ and } |E(G)| = n(4p + 1) + (n-1)$$

Define the vertex labeling $f: V(G) \rightarrow \{-1, 1\}$ by

$$f(u_{1,k}) = (-1)^{k+1} \text{ for } 1 \leq k \leq p-1,$$

$$f(x_1) = -1, f(y_1) = 1 \text{ and } f(z_1) = 1,$$

$$f(u_{2,k}) = (-1)^{k+1} \text{ for } 1 \leq k \leq p-1,$$

$$f(x_2) = -1, f(y_2) = 1 \text{ and } f(z_2) = 1,$$

⋮

$$f(u_{n,k}) = (-1)^{k+1} \text{ for } 1 \leq k \leq p-1,$$

$$f(x_n) = -1, f(y_n) = 1 \text{ and } f(z_n) = 1, f(u_{n,p}) = -1.$$

Note that $|V_f(-1)| = n(\frac{p-1}{2} + 2)$ and $|V_f(1)| = n(\frac{p-1}{2} + 2)$

Then the induced edge labeling $f^*: E(G) \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$ is given by

$$f^*(u_{1,i}u_{1,p}) = \begin{cases} 1 & i \text{ is odd} \\ 0 & i \text{ is even;} \end{cases} 1 \leq i \leq p-1$$

$$f^*(u_{2,i}u_{2,p}) = \begin{cases} 1 & i \text{ is odd} \\ 0 & i \text{ is even;} \end{cases} 1 \leq i \leq p-1$$

$$f^*(u_{n,i}u_{n,p}) = \begin{cases} 1 & i \text{ is odd} \\ 0 & i \text{ is even;} \end{cases} 1 \leq i \leq p-1$$

$$f^*(u_{1,i}z_1) = f^*(u_{1,i}y_1) = \begin{cases} 1 & i \text{ is even} \\ 0 & i \text{ is odd;} \end{cases} 1 \leq i \leq p-1$$

$$f^*(u_{2,i}z_1) = f^*(u_{2,i}y_2) = \begin{cases} 1 & i \text{ is even} \\ 0 & i \text{ is odd;} \end{cases} 1 \leq i \leq p-1.$$

⋮

$$f^*(u_{n,i}z_n) = f^*(u_{n,i}y_n) = \begin{cases} 1 & i \text{ is even} \\ 0 & i \text{ is odd;} \end{cases} 1 \leq i \leq p-1$$

$$f^*(u_{1,i}x_1) = f^*(u_{2,i}x_2) = \dots = f^*(u_{n,i}x_n) = \begin{cases} 0 & i \text{ is even} \\ 1 & i \text{ is odd.} \end{cases} 1 \leq i \leq p-1$$

$$f^*(u_{1,p}x_1) = f^*(u_{2,p}x_2) = \dots = f^*(u_{n,p}x_n) = 0$$

$$f^*(u_{1,p}y_1) = f^*(u_{2,p}y_2) = \dots = f^*(u_{n,p}y_n) = 1$$

$$f^*(u_{1,p}z_1) = f^*(u_{2,p}z_2) = \dots = f^*(u_{n,p}z_n) = 1$$

$$f^*(x_1y_1) = f^*(x_2y_2) = \dots = f^*(x_ny_n) = 1$$

$$f^*(y_1z_1) = f^*(y_2z_2) = \dots = f^*(y_nz_n) = 0$$

$$f^*(u_{i,p}u_{i+1,p}) = 0; 1 \leq i \leq n-1.$$

From the above

$$|e_{f^*}(1)| = (\frac{4(p-1)}{2} + 3)n \text{ and } |e_{f^*}(0)| = (\frac{4(p-1)}{2} + 2)n + (n-1)$$

Thus, it satisfies the condition $|e_{f^*}(0) - e_{f^*}(1)| \leq 1$.

Therefore, G is Group Difference Cordial graph.

Example 3.8

$P(3, (\Gamma(Z_{10}) + \Gamma(Z_6)))$ admits the group difference cordial labeling which is shown in figure 8.

$$V(\Gamma(Z_{10}) + \Gamma(Z_6)) = \{u_1, u_2, u_3, u_4, u_5, x, y, z\}$$

$$= \{2, 4, 6, 8, 5, x, y, z\} \text{ where } x=2 \text{ and } y=3 \text{ and } z = 4 \in Z_6$$

$$E(\Gamma(Z_{10}) + \Gamma(Z_6)) = \{u_i u_5, u_i x, u_i y, u_i z, u_5 x, u_5 y, u_5 z, x y, y z / 1 \leq i \leq 4\}.$$

$$|V(\Gamma(Z_{10}) + \Gamma(Z_6))| = 8 \text{ and } |E(\Gamma(Z_{2p}) + \Gamma(Z_9))| = 21.$$

Let $G = P(3, (\Gamma(Z_{10}) + \Gamma(Z_6)))$ where $n=3$ and $p=5$ then

$$|V(G)| = 24 \text{ and } |E(G)| = 65$$

Define the vertex labeling $f: V(G) \rightarrow \{-1, 1\}$ by

$$f(u_{1,k}) = (-1)^{k+1} \text{ for } 1 \leq k \leq 4,$$

$$f(x_1) = -1, f(y_1) = 1 \text{ and } f(z_1) = 1,$$

$$f(u_{2,k}) = (-1)^{k+1} \text{ for } 1 \leq k \leq 4,$$

$$f(x_2) = -1, f(y_2) = 1 \text{ and } f(z_2) = 1,$$

$$f(u_{3,k}) = (-1)^{k+1} \text{ for } 1 \leq k \leq 4,$$

$$f(x_3) = -1, f(y_3) = 1 \text{ and } f(z_3) = 1.$$

Note that $|v_f(-1)| = 12$ and $|v_f(1)| = 12$
 Then the induced edge labeling $f^*: E(G) \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$ is given by

$$f^*(u_{1,i}u_{1,5}) = \begin{cases} 1 & i \text{ is odd} \\ 0 & i \text{ is even;} \end{cases} 1 \leq i \leq 4$$

$$f^*(u_{2,i}u_{2,5}) = \begin{cases} 1 & i \text{ is odd} \\ 0 & i \text{ is even;} \end{cases} 1 \leq i \leq 4$$

$$f^*(u_{3,i}u_{3,5}) = \begin{cases} 1 & i \text{ is odd} \\ 0 & i \text{ is even;} \end{cases} 1 \leq i \leq 4$$

Type equation here.

$$f^*(u_{1,i}z_1) = f^*(u_{1,i}y_1) = \begin{cases} 1 & i \text{ is even} \\ 0 & i \text{ is odd;} \end{cases} 1 \leq i \leq 4$$

$$f^*(u_{2,i}z_2) = f^*(u_{2,i}y_2) = \begin{cases} 1 & i \text{ is even} \\ 0 & i \text{ is odd;} \end{cases} 1 \leq i \leq 4$$

$$f^*(u_{3,i}z_3) = f^*(u_{n,i}y_3) = \begin{cases} 1 & i \text{ is even} \\ 0 & i \text{ is odd;} \end{cases} 1 \leq i \leq 4$$

$$f^*(u_{1,i}x_1) = f^*(u_{2,i}x_2) = f^*(u_{3,i}x_3) = \begin{cases} 0 & i \text{ is even} \\ 1 & i \text{ is odd.} \end{cases} 1 \leq i \leq 4$$

$$f^*(u_{1,5}x_1) = f^*(u_{2,5}x_2) = f^*(u_{3,5}x_3) = 0$$

$$f^*(u_{1,5}y_1) = f^*(u_{2,5}y_2) = f^*(u_{3,5}y_3) = 1$$

$$f^*(u_{1,5}z_1) = f^*(u_{2,5}z_2) = f^*(u_{3,5}z_3) = 1$$

$$f^*(x_1y_1) = f^*(x_2y_2) = f^*(x_3y_3) = 1$$

$$f^*(y_1z_1) = f^*(y_2z_2) = f^*(y_3z_3) = 0$$

$$f^*(u_{1,5}u_{2,5}) = f^*(u_{2,5}u_{3,5}) = 0$$

From the above

$$|e_{f^*}(0)| = 32 \text{ and } |e_{f^*}(1)| = 33$$

Thus $|e_{f^*}(0) - e_{f^*}(1)| \leq 1$.

Therefore, G is Group Difference Cordial graph.

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figure 8: $P(3, (\Gamma(Z_{10}) + \Gamma(Z_6)))$

Theorem 3.9. For any prime number $p > 2$, the path union graph $P(n, (\overline{\Gamma(Z_{p^2})} + \Gamma(Z_9)))$ is a Group difference cordial graph.

Proof:

The vertex and edge set of $(\overline{\Gamma(Z_{p^2})} + \Gamma(Z_9))$ are

$$V(\overline{\Gamma(Z_{p^2})} + \Gamma(Z_9)) = \{u_1, u_2, u_3, \dots, u_{p-1}, x, y\}$$

$$= \{p, 2p, \dots, (p-1)p, x, y\} \text{ where } x=3 \text{ and } y=6 \in Z_9$$

$$E(\overline{\Gamma(Z_{p^2})} + \Gamma(Z_9)) = \{u_i x, u_i y, x y \mid 1 \leq i \leq p-1\}.$$

$$|V(\overline{\Gamma(Z_{p^2})} + \Gamma(Z_9))| = p+1 \text{ and } |E(\overline{\Gamma(Z_{p^2})} + \Gamma(Z_9))| = 2p-1.$$

Let $G = P(n, (\overline{\Gamma(Z_{p^2})} + \Gamma(Z_9)))$, There the vertex set of the graph G is

$$V(G) = \{u_{1,1}, u_{1,2}, \dots, u_{1,p-1}, x_1, y_1, \\ u_{2,1}, u_{2,2}, \dots, u_{2,p-1}, x_2, y_2, \\ \dots \\ u_{n,1}, u_{n,2}, \dots, u_{n,p-1}, u_{n,p}, x_n, y_n\}$$

and the edge set of G is

$$E(G) = \{u_{1,i}x_1, u_{1,i}y_1, x_1y_1, \dots, u_{n,i}x_n, u_{n,i}y_n, x_jx_{j+1} / 1 \leq i \leq p-1 \ \& \ 1 \leq j \leq n-1\}$$

Note that $|V| = n(p+1)$ and $|E| = n(2p-1) + (n-1)$

Define the vertex labeling

$$f: V(G) \rightarrow \{-1, 1\} \text{ by} \\ f(u_{1,k}) = (-1)^k \text{ for } 1 \leq k \leq p-1, \\ f(u_{2,k}) = (-1)^{k+1} \text{ for some } 1 \leq k \leq p-1, \\ \dots \\ f(u_{n,k}) = (-1)^k \text{ for some } 1 \leq k \leq p-1, \text{ if } n \text{ is odd} \\ f(u_{n,k}) = (-1)^{k+1} \text{ for some } 1 \leq k \leq p-1, \text{ if } n \text{ is even}$$

$$f(x_1) = -1, f(x_2) = -1, \dots, f(x_n) = -1, \\ f(y_1) = 1, f(y_2) = 1, \dots, f(y_n) = 1,$$

clearly, $|v_f(-1)| = n(\frac{p-1}{2} + 1)$ and $|v_f(1)| = n(\frac{p-1}{2} + 1)$

Then the induced edge labeling

$$f^*: E(G) \rightarrow \{0, 1\} \text{ is given by}$$

$$\text{if } n \text{ is odd } f^*(u_{n,i}, x_n) = \begin{cases} 1 & i \text{ is even} \\ 0 & i \text{ is odd} \end{cases}; 1 \leq i \leq p-1$$

$$\text{if } n \text{ is even } f^*(u_{n,i}, x_n) = \begin{cases} 0 & i \text{ is even} \\ 1 & i \text{ is odd} \end{cases}; 1 \leq i \leq p-1$$

$$\text{if } n \text{ is odd } f^*(u_{n,i}, y_n) = \begin{cases} 0 & i \text{ is even} \\ 1 & i \text{ is odd} \end{cases}; 1 \leq i \leq p-1$$

$$\text{if } n \text{ is even } f^*(u_{n,i}, y_n) = \begin{cases} 1 & i \text{ is even} \\ 0 & i \text{ is odd} \end{cases}; 1 \leq i \leq p-1$$

$$\text{and } f^*(x_1y_1) = f^*(x_2y_2) = \dots = f^*(x_ny_n) = 1.$$

From the above

$$|e_{f^*}(1)| = np \text{ and } |e_{f^*}(0)| = n(p-1) + (n-1) = np-1$$

and satisfies $|e_{f^*}(0) - e_{f^*}(1)| \leq 1$.

Hence G is Group difference Cordial graph. □

Example 3.10:

$P(3, (\overline{\Gamma(Z_{25})} + \Gamma(Z_9)))$ admits the group difference cordial labeling which is shown in figure 9.

Let $G = P(3, (\overline{\Gamma(Z_{25})} + \Gamma(Z_9)))$ where $p=5$ and $n=3$ then

the vertex set of the graph G is

$$V(G) = \{u_{1,1}, u_{1,2}, \dots, u_{1,4}, x_1, y_1, \\ u_{2,1}, u_{2,2}, \dots, u_{2,4}, x_2, y_2, \\ u_{3,1}, u_{3,2}, \dots, u_{3,4}, x_3, y_3\}$$

and the edge set of G is

$$E(G) = \{u_{1,i}x_1, u_{1,i}y_1, x_1y_1, u_{2,i}x_2, u_{2,i}y_2, x_2y_2, u_{3,i}x_3, u_{3,i}y_3, x_1x_2, x_2x_3, / 1 \leq i \leq 4\}$$

Note that $|V(G)| = 18$ and $|E(G)| = 29$

Define the vertex labeling

$$f: V(G) \rightarrow \{-1, 1\} \text{ by} \\ f(u_{1,k}) = (-1)^k \text{ for } 1 \leq k \leq 4,$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 f(u_{2,k}) &= (-1)^{k+1} \text{ for some } 1 \leq k \leq 4, \\
 f(u_{3,k}) &= (-1)^k \text{ for some } 1 \leq k \leq 4, \\
 f(x_1) &= -1, f(x_2) = -1, \dots, f(x_n) = -1, \\
 f(y_1) &= 1, f(y_2) = 1, \dots, f(y_n) = 1,
 \end{aligned}$$

clearly, $|v_f(-1)| = 9$ and $|v_f(1)| = 9$

Then the induced edge labeling

$f^*: E(G) \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$ is given by

$$f^*(u_{1,i}x_1) = \begin{cases} 1 & i \text{ is even} \\ 0 & i \text{ is odd} \end{cases}; 1 \leq i \leq 4$$

$$f^*(u_{2,i}x_2) = \begin{cases} 1 & i \text{ is even} \\ 0 & i \text{ is odd} \end{cases}; 1 \leq i \leq 4$$

$$f^*(u_{3,i}x_3) = \begin{cases} 1 & i \text{ is even} \\ 0 & i \text{ is odd} \end{cases}; 1 \leq i \leq 4$$

$$f^*(u_{1,i}y_1) = \begin{cases} 0 & i \text{ is even} \\ 1 & i \text{ is odd} \end{cases}; 1 \leq i \leq 4$$

$$f^*(u_{2,i}y_2) = \begin{cases} 1 & i \text{ is even} \\ 0 & i \text{ is odd} \end{cases}; 1 \leq i \leq 4$$

$$f^*(u_{3,i}y_3) = \begin{cases} 0 & i \text{ is even} \\ 1 & i \text{ is odd} \end{cases}; 1 \leq i \leq 4$$

and $f^*(x_1y_1) = f^*(x_2y_2) = f^*(x_3y_3) = 1$.

From the above labeling conditions

$$|e_{f^*}(1)| = 15 \text{ and } |e_{f^*}(0)| = 14$$

and satisfies the condition $|e_{f^*}(0) - e_{f^*}(1)| \leq 1$.

Hence G is Group difference Cordial graph. □

figure 9: $P(3, (\overline{\Gamma(Z_{25})} + \Gamma(Z_9)))$

Corollary 3.11:

For any prime number $p > 2$, the path union graph $P(n, (\overline{\Gamma(Z_{25})} + \Gamma(Z_9)))$, $n=2$ is group difference cordial graph.

Example 3.12: $P(2, (\overline{\Gamma(Z_{25})} + \Gamma(Z_9)))$ admits the group difference cordial labeling which is shown in figure 10.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Here } |v_f(-1)| &= 6 \text{ and } |v_f(1)| = 6, \\
 |e_{f^*}(0)| &= 9 \text{ and } |e_{f^*}(1)| = 8
 \end{aligned}$$

hence $P(2, (\overline{\Gamma(Z_{25})} + \overline{\Gamma(Z_9)}))$ is Group Difference Cordial graph.

figure 10: $P(2, (\overline{\Gamma(Z_{25})} + \overline{\Gamma(Z_9)}))$

Theorem 3.13. For any prime number $p > 2$, the path union graph $P(2, (\overline{\Gamma(Z_{p^2})} + \Gamma(Z_6)))$ is GDC graph.

Proof:

The vertex and edge set of $(\overline{\Gamma(Z_{p^2})} + \Gamma(Z_6))$ are

$$V(\overline{\Gamma(Z_{p^2})} + \Gamma(Z_6)) = \{u_1, u_2, u_3, \dots, u_{p-1}, x, y, z\}$$

$$= \{p, 2p, \dots, (p-1)p, x, y, z\} \text{ where } x=2 \text{ and } y=3, z=4 \in Z_6$$

$$E(\overline{\Gamma(Z_{p^2})} + \Gamma(Z_6)) = \{u_i x, u_i y, u_i z, x y, y z / 1 \leq i \leq p-1\}.$$

$$|V(\overline{\Gamma(Z_{p^2})} + \Gamma(Z_6))| = p+2 \text{ and } |E(\overline{\Gamma(Z_{p^2})} + \Gamma(Z_6))| = 3p-1.$$

Let $G = P(2, (\overline{\Gamma(Z_{p^2})} + \Gamma(Z_6)))$ Then the vertex set of the graph G is

$$V(G) = \{u_{1,1}, u_{1,2}, \dots, u_{1,p-1}, x_1, y_1, z_1,$$

$$u_{2,1}, u_{2,2}, \dots, u_{2,p-1}, x_2, y_2, z_2\}$$

The edge set of G is

$$E(G) = \{u_{1,i}x_1, u_{1,i}y_1, u_{1,i}z_1, x_1y_1, y_1z_1,$$

$$u_{2,i}x_2, u_{2,i}y_2, u_{2,i}z_2, x_2y_2, y_2z_2, u_{1,1}u_{2,p-1} / 1 \leq i \leq p-1\}.$$

Note that

$$|V(G)| = 2(p+2) \text{ and } |E(G)| = 2(3p-1) + 1 = 6p-1$$

Define the vertex labeling $f: V(G) \rightarrow \{-1, 1\}$ by

$$f(u_{1,k}) = (-1)^k \text{ for } 1 \leq k \leq p-1,$$

$$f(u_{2,k}) = (-1)^k \text{ for } 1 \leq k \leq p-1,$$

$$f(x_1) = -1, f(y_1) = -1, f(z_1) = 1,$$

$$f(x_2) = 1, f(y_2) = 1, f(z_2) = -1,$$

clearly $|v_f(-1)| = p+2$ and $|v_f(1)| = p+2$

Then the induced edge labeling $f^*: E(G) \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$ is given by

$$f^*(u_{1,i}x_1) = f^*(u_{1,i}y_1) = \begin{cases} 1 & i \text{ is even} \\ 0 & i \text{ is odd} \end{cases}; 1 \leq i \leq p-1$$

$$f^*(u_{1,i}z_1) = \begin{cases} 0 & i \text{ is even} \\ 1 & i \text{ is odd} \end{cases}; 1 \leq i \leq p-1$$

$$f^*(u_{2,i}x_2) = f^*(u_{2,i}y_2) = \begin{cases} 1 & i \text{ is odd} \\ 0 & i \text{ is even} \end{cases}; 1 \leq i \leq p-1$$

$$f^*(u_{2,i}z_2) = \begin{cases} 0 & i \text{ is odd} \\ 1 & i \text{ is even} \end{cases}; 1 \leq i \leq p-1$$

$$f^*(u_{1,1}u_{2,p-1}) = 1,$$

$$f^*(x_1y_1) = 0,$$

$$f^*(y_1z_1) = 1,$$

$$f^*(x_2y_2) = 0,$$

$$f^*(y_2z_2) = 1.$$

From the above

$$|e_{f^*}(1)| = 3p \text{ and } |e_{f^*}(0)| = 3p-1 \text{ and satisfies } |e_{f^*}(0) - e_{f^*}(1)| \leq 1.$$

Hence G is group difference cordial graph. □

Example 3.14:

Let $G = P(2, (\overline{\Gamma(Z_{p^2})} + \Gamma(Z_6)))$ where $p=5$ then $G = P(2, (\overline{\Gamma(Z_{25})} + \Gamma(Z_6)))$ the vertex set of the graph G is

$$V(G) = \{u_{1,1}, u_{1,2}, u_{1,3}, u_{1,4}, x_1, y_1, z_1, u_{2,1}, u_{2,2}, u_{2,3}, u_{2,4}, x_2, y_2, z_2\}$$

The edge set of G is

$$E(G) = \{u_{1,i}x_1, u_{1,i}y_1, u_{1,i}z_1, x_1y_1, y_1z_1, u_{2,i}x_2, u_{2,i}y_2, u_{2,i}z_2, x_2y_2, y_2z_2, u_{1,1}u_{2,1} \mid 1 \leq i \leq 4\}.$$

Note that

$$|V| = 14 \text{ and } |E| = 29$$

Define the vertex labeling $f: V(G) \rightarrow \{-1, 1\}$ by

$$f(u_{1,k}) = (-1)^k \text{ for } 1 \leq k \leq 4,$$

$$f(u_{2,k}) = (-1)^k \text{ for } 1 \leq k \leq 4,$$

$$f(x_1) = -1, f(y_1) = -1, f(z_1) = 1,$$

$$f(x_2) = 1, f(y_2) = 1, f(z_2) = -1,$$

clearly $|v_f(-1)| = 7$ and $|v_f(1)| = 7$

Then the induced edge labeling $f^*: E(G) \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$ is given by

$$f^*(u_{1,i}x_1) = f^*(u_{1,i}y_1) = \begin{cases} 1 & i \text{ is even} \\ 0 & i \text{ is odd} \end{cases} \quad 1 \leq i \leq 4$$

$$f^*(u_{1,i}z_1) = \begin{cases} 0 & i \text{ is even} \\ 1 & i \text{ is odd} \end{cases} \quad 1 \leq i \leq 4$$

$$f^*(u_{2,i}x_2) = f^*(u_{2,i}y_2) = \begin{cases} 1 & i \text{ is odd} \\ 0 & i \text{ is even} \end{cases} \quad 1 \leq i \leq 4$$

$$f^*(u_{2,i}z_2) = \begin{cases} 0 & i \text{ is odd} \\ 1 & i \text{ is even} \end{cases} \quad 1 \leq i \leq 4$$

$$f^*(u_{1,1}u_{2,4}) = 1,$$

$$f^*(x_1y_1) = 0,$$

$$f^*(y_1z_1) = 1,$$

$$f^*(x_2y_2) = 0,$$

$$f^*(y_2z_2) = 1.$$

From the above,

$$|e_{f^*}(1)| = 15 \text{ and } |e_{f^*}(0)| = 14 \text{ and satisfies the condition } |e_{f^*}(0) - e_{f^*}(1)| \leq 1.$$

Hence G is a group difference cordial graph. □

figure 11: $P(2, (\overline{\Gamma(Z_{p^2})} + \Gamma(Z_6)))$

Corollary 3.15:

For any prime number $p > 2$, the path union graph $P(2, (\overline{\Gamma(Z_{p^2})} + \overline{\Gamma(Z_6)}))$ does not admit a Group difference cordial labeling.

Example 3.16:

A group difference cordial labeling of the graph $P(2, (\overline{\Gamma(Z_{25})} + \overline{\Gamma(Z_6)}))$ is given in figure 12.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Here } |v_f(-1)| &= 7 \text{ and } |v_f(1)| = 7, \\ |e_{f^*}(1)| &= 15 \text{ and } |e_{f^*}(0)| = 12. \end{aligned}$$

Hence $P(2, (\overline{\Gamma(Z_{25})} + \overline{\Gamma(Z_6)}))$ is not a group difference cordial graph.

figure 12: $P(2, (\overline{\Gamma(Z_{25})} + \overline{\Gamma(Z_6)}))$

Theorem 3.17:

For any prime number $p \geq 3$ and positive integer m , the path union graph $P(2, ((\overline{\Gamma(Z_{p^2})} + m \Gamma(Z_4)))$ is Group difference cordial graph.

Proof:

The vertex and edge set of $(\overline{\Gamma(Z_{p^2})} + m \Gamma(Z_4))$ are

$$V(\overline{\Gamma(Z_{p^2})} + m \Gamma(Z_4)) = \{u_1, u_2, u_3, \dots, u_{p-1}, v_1, v_2, \dots, v_m\}$$

$$E(\overline{\Gamma(Z_{p^2})} + m \Gamma(Z_4)) = \{u_i v_j \mid 1 \leq i \leq p-1, 1 \leq j \leq m\}.$$

$$|V(\overline{\Gamma(Z_{p^2})} + m \Gamma(Z_4))| = p+m-1 \text{ and } |E(\overline{\Gamma(Z_{p^2})} + m \Gamma(Z_4))| = m(p-1).$$

Let $G = P(2, ((\overline{\Gamma(Z_{p^2})} + m \Gamma(Z_4)))$ where p is a prime number and m is a positive integer.

The vertex set

$$V(G) = \{u_{1,1}, u_{1,2}, \dots, u_{1,p-1}, v_{1,1}, v_{1,2}, \dots, v_{1,m}, u_{2,1}, u_{2,2}, \dots, u_{2,p-1}, v_{2,1}, v_{2,2}, \dots, v_{2,m}\}$$

and the edge set of

$$E(G) = \{u_{1,i} v_{1,j}, u_{2,i} v_{2,j}, u_{1,i} u_{2,p-1} \mid 1 \leq i \leq p-1, 1 \leq j \leq m\}.$$

Clearly $|V(G)| = 2(p+m-1)$; and

$$|E(G)| = 2m(p-1) + 1.$$

Define the vertex labeling $f: V(G) \rightarrow \{-1, 1\}$ by

$$f(u_{1,i}) = \begin{cases} -1, & i \text{ is odd} \\ 1, & i \text{ is even} \end{cases} \quad \text{for } 1 \leq i \leq p-1$$

$$f(u_{2,i}) = \begin{cases} -1, & i \text{ is odd} \\ 1, & i \text{ is even} \end{cases} \quad \text{for } 1 \leq i \leq p-1$$

$$f(v_{1,j}) = \begin{cases} -1, & j \text{ is odd} \\ 1, & j \text{ is even} \end{cases} \quad \text{for } 1 \leq j \leq m$$

$$f(v_{2,j}) = \begin{cases} 1, & j \text{ is odd} \\ -1, & j \text{ is even} \end{cases} \quad \text{for } 1 \leq j \leq m$$

Case 1: Where m is even, $|v_f(-1)| = p-1+m$ and $|v_f(1)| = p-1+m$.

Case 2: Where m is odd, $|v_f(-1)| = p+m$ and $|v_f(1)| = p+m$

Clearly $|v_f(-1) - v_f(1)| \leq 1$.

The induced edge labeling $f^*: E(G) \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$ by

$$f^*(u_{1,i}v_{1,j}) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{both } i \text{ and } j \text{ are even (or) both } i \text{ and } j \text{ are odd} \\ 1 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

$$f^*(u_{2,i}v_{2,j}) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{both } i \text{ and } j \text{ are even (or) both } i \text{ and } j \text{ are odd} \\ 1 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

$$f^*(u_{1,1}u_{2,4}) = 1$$

We observe that,

$$|e_{f^*}(0)| = m(p-1) \text{ and } |e_{f^*}(1)| = m(p-1) + 1$$

Thus, $|e_{f^*}(0) - e_{f^*}(1)| \leq 1$.

Therefore, G is Group Difference Cordial graph.

□

Example 4.18: A group difference cordial labeling of the graph P (2. $(\overline{\Gamma(Z_{25})} + 3\Gamma(Z_4))$) is given in figure 13.

Here $|v_f(-1)| = 7$ and $|v_f(1)| = 7$,

$|e_f(1)| = 13$ and $|e_f(0)| = 12$ and hence P (2. $(\overline{\Gamma(Z_{25})} + 3\Gamma(Z_4))$) is a group difference cordial graph.

figure 13: P (2. $(\overline{\Gamma(Z_{25})} + 3\Gamma(Z_4))$)

4. CONCLUSION

The path union graphs

- $P(n.(\Gamma(Z_{2p}) + \Gamma(Z_4)))$, $n \geq 2$ and $p > 2$ is a GDC graph.
- $P(n.(\Gamma(Z_{2p}) + \Gamma(Z_6)))$, $n \geq 2$ and $p > 2$ is a GDC graph.
- $P(n.(\Gamma(Z_{2p}) + \overline{\Gamma(Z_6)}))$, $n \geq 2$ and $p > 2$ is not a GDC graph.
- $P(n.(\Gamma(Z_{2p}) + \Gamma(Z_9)))$, admits GDC labeling $n = 2$ and $p > 2$ and does not admit GDC labeling if $n > 2$.
- $P(n.(\Gamma(Z_{2p}) + \overline{\Gamma(Z_9)}))$, $n \geq 2$ and $p > 2$ is not a GDC graph.
- $P(n.(\overline{\Gamma(Z_{p^2})} + \Gamma(Z_9)))$, $n \geq 2$ and $p > 2$ is a GDC graph.
- $P(n.(\overline{\Gamma(Z_{p^2})} + \overline{\Gamma(Z_9)}))$, admits GDC labeling $n = 2$ and $p > 2$ and does not admit GDC labeling if $n > 2$.
- $P(n.(\overline{\Gamma(Z_{p^2})} + \Gamma(Z_6)))$, $n = 2$ and $p > 2$ is a GDC graph and does not admit if $n > 2$.
- $P(n.(\overline{\Gamma(Z_{p^2})} + \overline{\Gamma(Z_6)}))$, $n \geq 2$ and $p > 2$ is not a GDC graph.
- $P(n.(\overline{\Gamma(Z_{p^2})} + m\Gamma(Z_4)))$, admits GDC labeling $n = 2$ and $p > 2$ and does not admit GDC labeling if $n > 2$.

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